

Studies on some Complex Chromiselenates. Part I.

BY PULIN BIHARI SARKAR AND SAILENDRA NATH BHATTACHARYA.

Chromium sulphates, both green and violet, have been exhaustively studied; complex chromosulphuric acids and their salts have likewise been investigated.

Sulphur and selenium are members of the sixth group of the Periodic Table. They present striking analogy both in the elements themselves and in their salts. Thus the selenates and the sulphates of the alkali metals are perfectly isomorphous. Chromoselenic alums and chromosulphuric alums are also isomorphous. A search for the literature shows that in recent years, like the green and violet chromium sulphates, Meyer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, 118, 1) prepared the corresponding green and violet chromium selenates. The violet salts of chromium are generally the aquo-salts while the green salts are all complex compounds having some negative radicles dissimulated in the complex cation. Beautiful examples of these are to be found in the isomeric hexahydrated chromic chlorides:

$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_3$, violet salt of Recoura;

$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, green salt of Bjerrum;

$[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, green salt of Recoura.

Green chromium sulphate can combine with one, two or three molecules of sulphuric acid or alkali sulphates to form complex chromosulphuric acids and chromosulphates which have been studied by Recoura (*Compt. rend.*, 1892, 114, 477).

In the present paper we have studied the formation of chromoselenic acid, chromosulphoselenic acids and their salts. Their composition and chemical properties are exactly similar to those of Recoura's compounds. A study of the dehydration products of pure and mixed chromoselenic alums is in progress. The alums $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3$, $\text{Na}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SeO}_4 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$

have been found to lose at 26-27° over sulphuric acid in a desiccator twelve molecules of water of crystallisation. This is in accordance with the behaviour of the other chromosulphuric alums studied by Lowell (*Ann. chim.-phys.*, 1855, *iii*, 44, 320), Müller-Erzbach (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 2, 113) and Lesceur and Mathurin (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1888, 80, 33).

The alums after dehydration still remain violet. They are soluble in water and in aqueous solution behave as double salts and readily give the tests for the constituent ions. Progressive dehydration at higher temperatures changes the colour to green and although they still remain soluble in water, the reactions of chromium, sulphate or selenate ions are masked in the freshly prepared solution in the cold, as is to be expected. A detailed investigation of this will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

The complex acids and salts already referred to above are all green and hygroscopic crystalline substances, soluble in water, to which they impart the same colour. In the freshly prepared aqueous solution ammonia gives no precipitate of chromium hydroxide, nor does barium chloride precipitate either the selenate or the sulphate ion. But if the cold solution be heated, the respective precipitates may be made to appear, clearly showing that they are all within a complex molecule. The complexes are not, however, very stable, as they break down in solution even at the ordinary room temperature (30°) when kept for about half an hour.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Green chromium selenate has been prepared according to the method of Meyer (*loc. cit.*). It may be mentioned here that Meyer's method for the preparation of violet chromium selenate requires certain modifications as difficulties were experienced in preparing it, no doubt, owing to the rise in temperature.

Preparation of Violet Chromium Selenate.—Five parts of chromium nitrate were dissolved in the least quantity of cold water and then cooled in ice and salt mixture. To it was poured a solution of seven parts of sodium selenate dissolved in the least quantity of water which was also previously cooled in ice and salt. By careful use of a strong freezing mixture, the temperature was kept as low as 0°. Glacial acetic acid was then added drop by drop with frequent stirring during which the temperature was kept below 3°, when crude violet chromium selenate was obtained. It was then dissolved in

the least quantity of cold water and precipitated by 96% alcohol. The process was repeated to get a purer product.

If the temperature be allowed to rise above 10° during the addition of acetic acid or if the acetic acid be added very rapidly, only the green product is obtained.

Preparation of the Chromoselenic Acids and their Salts.—In preparing chromoselenic acid, green chromium selenate and selenic acid were taken in exactly molecular proportions. The chromium selenate was dissolved in the least quantity of water and mixed with the selenic acid and heated on the water-bath to dryness. The residue thus obtained was then dried in an electrically heated air-oven at 120° to constant weight. By employing one, two or three molecular proportions of sulphuric acid or potassium sulphate instead of the selenic acid, in the above process, the corresponding mono-, di-, or tri-sulphoselenic acids or their potassium salts were obtained.

Chromoselenic Acid.—It is a green crystalline substance, soluble in cold water and very hygroscopic. Chromium and selenium cannot be detected in the freshly prepared cold aqueous solution. (Found: Cr, 15.1; Se, 46.2. $\text{HCr}(\text{SeO}_4)_2$ requires Cr, 15.3; Se, 46.6 per cent.). Its properties clearly indicate that the constitution is $\text{H}[\text{Cr}(\text{SeO}_4)_2]$.

Chromoselenomonosulphuric Acid.—It is a green crystalline powder and very hygroscopic. The chromic, sulphate and the selenate ions are all within a complex ion and therefore a cold freshly prepared solution does not give tests for these ions. (Found: Cr, 16.7; Se, 37.4; SO_4 , 15.3. $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3\text{SO}_4$ requires Cr, 16.5; Se, 37.4; SO_4 , 15.2 per cent.).

The constitution of the compound is

Chromoselenodisulphuric Acid.—It is a green crystalline powder, which rapidly absorbs moisture from the air. Its other properties are also similar to those described above. (Found: Cr, 14.0; Se, 32.5; SO_4 , 26.4. $\text{H}_4\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3(\text{SO}_4)_2$ requires Cr, 14.2; Se, 32.5; SO_4 , 26.8 per cent.).

The constitution of the compound is

Chromoselenotrisulphuric Acid.—It is a green crystalline substance and very hygroscopic. Its other properties are very similar to those described above. (Found: Cr, 18.4; Se, 29.4; SO₄, 35.6. H₆Cr₂(SeO₄)₃(SO₄)₃ requires Cr, 18.6; Se, 28.6; SO₄, 35.5 per cent.).

The constitution of the compound is

Potassium Chromoselenomonosulphate.—Its properties are very similar to acids but the hygroscopic character is less pronounced. (Found: Cr, 14.9; Se, 33.75; SO₄, 13.4. K₂Cr₂(SeO₄)₃(SO₄) requires Cr, 14.6; Se, 33.52; SO₄, 13.5 per cent.). It is evi-

dently the potassium salt of the acid $\text{H}_2 \left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{SeO}_4)_3 \\ \text{Cr}_2 \\ (\text{SO}_4) \end{array} \right]$.

Potassium Chromoselenodisulphate.—It is a green crystalline substance. Its hygroscopic character is less than the corresponding acid. (Found: Cr, 12.0; Se, 26.7; SO₄, 21.8. K₄Cr₂(SeO₄)₃(SO₄)₂ requires Cr, 11.8; Se, 26.9; SO₄, 21.7 per cent.).

This compound is the potassium salt of the corresponding acid

Potassium Chromoselenotrisulphate.—It is a green crystalline substance and its properties closely resemble those of the corresponding acid. Only its hygroscopic character is less. (Found: Cr, 9.9; Se, 23.2; SO₄, 26.5. K₆Cr₂(SeO₄)₃(SO₄)₃ requires Cr, 9.9; Se, 23.4; SO₄, 26.3 per cent.).

It is the potassium salt of the acid

Incidentally we have prepared a mixed chromosulphoselenic alum which does not seem to have hitherto been described.

Preparation of Cr₂(SO₄)₃.Na₂(SeO₄).24H₂O.—Five g. of violet chromium sulphate dissolved in the least quantity of cold water are mixed with 2.4 g. of Na₂SeO₄ likewise dissolved in cold water. The

mixed solution is then allowed to concentrate in vacuum over sulphuric acid. After 24 hours violet octahedral crystals were obtained. They are exactly similar and isomorphous with the other chromoselenic and chromosulphuric alums. Its solution turned green when heated over 60°. (Found: Cr, 10·24; Se, 7·85. $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{Na}_2\text{SeO}_3 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cr, 10·23, Se, 7·8 per cent.).

Method of Analysis.

Case I. When the compounds contained selenium and no sulphur.—Ammonium hydroxide was added to the aqueous solution and strongly boiled when chromium hydroxide was preprecipitated which was then filtered, dried and ignited and weighed as Cr_2O_3 . The filtrate was then evaporated nearly to dryness with a few c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid to reduce the selenates to selenites. Sulphur dioxide was then passed through the solution for some time, when metallic selenium was precipitated which was filtered in a Gooch crucible dried and weighed as such.

Case II. When the compounds contained chromium, selenium and sulphur.—Chromium and selenium were estimated as above. For the estimation of the sulphate radicle a different sample must be taken. The aqueous solution was first boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid to reduce selenates to selenites, barium chloride solution was then added to precipitate barium sulphate. It was then filtered in a Gooch crucible, washed with alcohol and ether, dried and weighed.

